

A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON EFFICACY OF THREE DIFFERENT TREATMENT MODALITIES FOR TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT PAIN AND DYSFUNCTION

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ABSTRACT

Background: Temporomandibular disorders (TMDs) are a heterogeneous group of pathologies affecting the temporomandibular joint (TMJ), the jaw muscles, or both. Hence; the present study was planned for assessing efficacy of three different treatment modalities for temporomandibular joint pain and dysfunction.

Materials & methods: A total of 30 patients with presence of Temporomandibular Joint Pain and Dysfunction were enrolled. All the patients were divided into three study groups as follows: Group 1- Patients treated with occlusal splint, Group 2- Patients treated with tens therapy, and Group 3- Patients treated with Pharmacotherapy. In all the study groups, if patient was not responding and severe discomfort and pain continued for more than 1 month, the patients were excluded. Follow-up was done and treatment response was evaluated. Perceived stress scale and VAS were used for follow-up assessment. All the results were recorded in Microsoft excel sheet and were analyzed by SPSS software.

Results: Mean perceived stress scale among the patients of group 1 at one month follow-up, two months follow-up and three months follow was 4.1, 2.5 and 1.9 respectively. Mean perceived stress scale among the patients of group 2 at one month follow-up, two months follow-up and three months follow was 4.2, 3.8 and 2.8 respectively. Mean perceived stress scale among the patients of group 3 at one month follow-up, two months follow-up and three months follow was 4, 4 and 3.5 respectively. Significant results were obtained while comparing the perceived stress scale among the three study groups at different time intervals. Mean VAS among the patients of group 1 at one month follow-up, two months follow-up and three months follow was 7.2, 7.5 and 8.3 respectively. Mean VAS among the patients of group 2 at one month follow-up, two months follow-up and three months follow was 2.5, 3.9 and 4.6 respectively. Mean VAS among the patients of group 3 at one month follow-up, two months follow-up and three months follow was 0.8, 1.5 and 2.9 respectively. Significant results were obtained while comparing the VAS among the three study groups at different time intervals.

Conclusion: From the above results, the authors concluded that in comparison to the tens therapy and pharmacotherapy, occlusal splint was the most effective in managing patients with Temporomandibular Joint Pain and Dysfunction.

Key words: Occlusal splint, Pain, Temporomandibular Joint

I. INTRODUCTION

Temporomandibular disorders (TMDs) are a heterogeneous group of pathologies affecting the temporomandibular joint (TMJ), the jaw muscles, or both. Epidemiological studies of TMD reveal a prevalence of 82% in the general population, and 48% of them presented with clinical features of muscle tenderness and difficulty in mouth opening. TMDs are considered to be the most common orofacial pain conditions of nondental origin. The frequent concurrent

presence of other symptoms such as earache, headache, neuralgia, and tooth pain which may be related to TMD or present as ancillary findings makes the assessment of TMD a complex issue.¹⁻³

The etiology of TMD is little understood, but has been associated with several factors including malocclusion, trauma, emotional stress, and parafunctional habits (clenching or bruxing). As a consequence of the multifactorial pathogenesis, therapeutic concepts must be interdisciplinary. Reversible conservative therapy such as cognitive behavioral therapy, physical therapy, pharmacological therapy and intraoral appliances should be considered for the first-line management of TMD. Splint therapy is performed using various types of stabilization, anterior positioning or bite plane appliances. Moreover, numerous forms of physical therapy intervention, including ultrasound (US) and transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS), can be potentially effective for management of TMD. TENS is a non-invasive intervention that turn-on a neural network system to decrease intensity of pain by actuating descending inhibitory system. TENS works by a phenomenon called “gate control theory”. These are multiple receptors in the periphery - pain, vibration, temperature, etc. - All of which transmit information to brain via spinal cord. It is safe, non-intellectual method.⁴⁻⁶ Hence; the present study was planned for assessing efficacy of three different treatment modalities for temporomandibular joint pain and dysfunction.

II. MATERIALS & METHODS

The present study was conducted with the aim of assessing efficacy of three different treatment modalities for temporomandibular joint pain and dysfunction. A total of 30 patients with presence of Temporomandibular Joint Pain and Dysfunction were enrolled. All the patients were divided into three study groups as follows:

- Group 1- Patients treated with occlusal splint
- Group 2- Patients treated with tens therapy, and
- Group 3- Patients treated with Pharmacotherapy

In all the study groups, if patient was not responding and severe discomfort and pain continued for more than 1 month, the patients were excluded. Follow-up was done and treatment response was evaluated. Perceived stress scale and VAS were used for follow-up assessment. All the results were recorded in Microsoft excel sheet and were analyzed by SPSS software. Chi-square test and one-way ANOVA were used for evaluation of level of significance.

III. RESULTS

In the present study, a total of 30 patients were enrolled and were divided into three study groups- Group 1, Group 2 and Group 3. Mean age of the patients of group 1, group 2 and group 3 was 29.8 years, 30.9 years and 31.7 years respectively. Majority of the patients among all the three study groups were males. Mean perceived stress scale among the patients of group 1 at one month follow-up, two months follow-up and three months follow was 4.1, 2.5 and 1.9 respectively. Mean perceived stress scale among the patients of group 2 at one month follow-up, two months follow-up and three months follow was 4.2, 3.8 and 2.8 respectively. Mean perceived stress scale among the patients of group 3 at one month follow-up, two months follow-up and three months follow was 4, 4 and 3.5 respectively. Significant results were obtained while comparing the perceived stress scale among the three study groups at different time intervals. Mean VAS among the patients of group 1 at one month follow-up, two months follow-up and three months follow was 7.2, 7.5 and 8.3 respectively. Mean VAS among the patients of group 2 at one month follow-up, two months follow-up and three months follow was 2.5, 3.9 and 4.6 respectively. Mean VAS among the patients of group 3 at one month follow-up, two months follow-up and three months follow was 0.8, 1.5 and 2.9 respectively. Significant results were obtained while comparing the VAS among the three study groups at different time intervals.

Table 1: Age-wise distribution of patients

Age group (years)	Group 1		Group 2		Group 3	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Less than 30	7	70	6	60	6	60
30 to 50	2	20	2	20	3	30
More than 50	1	10	2	20	1	10
Total	10	100	10	100	10	100

Table 2: Gender-wise distribution of patients

Gender	Group 1		Group 2		Group 3	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Males	6	60	7	70	6	60
Females	4	40	3	30	4	40
Total	10	100	10	100	10	100

Table 3: Comparison of Perceived stress scale at different time intervals

Time interval	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	p- value
One month follow-up	4.1	4.2	4	0.85
Two month follow-up	2.5	3.8	4	0.00*
Three month follow-up	1.9	2.8	3.5	0.00*

*: Significant

Table 4: Comparison of VAS at different time intervals

Time interval	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	p- value
One month follow-up	7.2	7.5	8.3	0.38
Two month follow-up	2.5	3.9	4.6	0.00*
Three month follow-up	0.8	1.5	2.9	0.00*

*: Significant

IV. DISCUSSION

Temporomandibular disorders (TMD) represent a heterogeneous group of pathologies affecting the temporomandibular joints, the jaw muscles, or both. They are the most common orofacial pain conditions of non-dental origin. They are frequently encountered in clinical practice, and their prevalence in the general population has been reported as being as high as 12%. Pain can be present at any stage of TMDs and is a significant part of the symptoms that prompt patients to seek treatment. Treatments for TMDs are wide-ranging and directed primarily toward relief from persistent orofacial pain.⁷⁻⁹ As TMDs share multifactorial etiology and many coexisting factors contribute in the progression and management of disease, it becomes disorienting to treat a TMD in the correct manner. Hence, the treatment of all TMDs cannot be same, and treatment plan for each type of TMD should follow a specific guideline by starting with conservative therapies such as physical therapy, pharmacotherapy, splint therapy, and more stringent nonconservative therapies (comprehensive occlusal rehabilitation and TMJ surgeries) should be considered only when former fails. As the nonconservative therapies are irreversible, they should be used only as the last resort; also reevaluation and long-term follow-up are obligatory for nonconservative therapies to ensure complete remission of the disease. While treating TMDs, challenge for clinician is to choose the correct type of splint although some studies suggested that success of splint therapy has less to do with the splint make or type and more to do with the primary disjunction of ingrained neuromuscular reflexes due to partial nonengagement of maxillary and mandibular teeth. The conventional routinely followed design, i.e., anterior repositioning appliance (ARA) requires regular and repeated evaluation with risk of posterior open bite in the long run. There are studies in literature suggesting centric stabilization splints (CSSs) show fewer problems in comparison to ARA after treatment and that soft splints (SSs) should be used more in cases of myofascial pain dysfunction syndrome (MPDS) than intracapsular TMDs.¹⁰⁻¹² Hence; the present study was planned for assessing efficacy of three different treatment modalities for temporomandibular joint pain and dysfunction.

In the present study, a total of 30 patients were enrolled and were divided into three study groups- Group 1, Group 2 and Group 3. Mean age of the patients of group 1, group 2 and group 3 was 29.8 years, 30.9 years and 31.7 years respectively. Majority of the patients among all the three study groups were males. Mean perceived stress scale among the patients of group 1 at one month follow-up, two months follow-up and three months follow was 4.1, 2.5 and 1.9 respectively. Mean perceived stress scale among the patients of group 2 at one month follow-up, two months follow-up and three months follow was 4.2, 3.8 and 2.8 respectively. Mean perceived stress scale among the patients of group 3 at one month follow-up, two months follow-up and three months follow was 4, 4 and 3.5 respectively. Significant results were obtained while comparing the perceived stress scale among the three study

groups at different time intervals. Our results were in concordance with the results obtained by Madani et al who also reported similar findings. In their study, authors evaluated the efficacy of three treatment options, including anterior positioning splint therapy, physical therapy, and physical therapy in addition to splint therapy, in terms of treatment outcome, in patients with painful temporomandibular joint clicking. Sixty patients suffering from acute pain and dysfunction were divided randomly into three treatment groups. Twenty patients underwent anterior positioning splint therapy (group I), 20 patients received solely physical therapy (group II), and 20 subjects received physical treatment in addition to splinting (group III). All patients were examined before and after the treatment using a visual analogue scale (VAS) and digital palpation of joint sounds. The data were analyzed using the Kruskal-Wallis, one-way ANOVA and Tukey tests at a significance level of $P < 0.05$. In comparison with the baseline, subjective pain was decreased significantly ($P < 0.05$) in all three groups. A significant difference was observed between groups I and II ($P < 0.05$). Anterior positioning splint therapy appears to be the best treatment method for reduction of pain and joint sounds in patients with TMD, compared with the other two methods studied.¹³

In the present study, Mean VAS among the patients of group 1 at one month follow-up, two months follow-up and three months follow was 7.2, 7.5 and 8.3 respectively. Mean VAS among the patients of group 2 at one month follow-up, two months follow-up and three months follow was 2.5, 3.9 and 4.6 respectively. Mean VAS among the patients of group 3 at one month follow-up, two months follow-up and three months follow was 0.8, 1.5 and 2.9 respectively. Significant results were obtained while comparing the VAS among the three study groups at different time intervals. Smith et al compared acupuncture with a placebo and concluded that the former exerts a positive influence on the signs and symptoms of myofascial TMD pain. Similarly in a previous study, Johansson et al compared groups treated with acupuncture and occlusal splints and found that both treatments satisfactorily reduced the symptoms of pain of muscular origin. However, this study had a short follow-up period (i.e. 3 months), and a longer follow-up time is required to completely assess the effects of acupuncture treatment.^{14, 15} In another study conducted by Devi J et al, authors assessed the effectiveness of different types of splint therapy over the conventional anterior repositioning appliance (ARA) group. Single-blind, randomized, comparative clinical trial conducted in thirty patients, 18–55 years of age, allocated to three groups, i.e., ARA conventional group, centric stabilization splint (CSS), and Soft splint (SS) groups. Preoperative values of comfortable mouth opening (CMO) in mm, maximum mouth opening (MMO) in mm, TMJ clicking and tenderness (grading 0–3), visual analog scale pain score (0–10 cm), and total energy (TE) integral values of both TMJs using JVA were recorded. Postoperative values were taken at the time of delivery of splint at 1st, 2nd, 6th, and 10th week. Intergroup comparison – Kruskal–Wallis test showed no statistically significant difference in CMO, MMO, and TE values of right TMJs among three groups at any point. No significant difference was seen in TMJ clicking and tenderness among groups at any point of time except at 10 weeks and at 2 weeks, respectively, by Chi-square test. Intragroup comparison - Wilcoxon signed-rank test showed the significance of difference ($P < 0.05^*$) in postoperative visits for CMO, MMO, pain score, and TE values. Clinical effect size, extent, consistency, and percentage of cases showing improvement were maximum for CSS group. The study concludes that the use of JVA for diagnosis along with history and clinical examination increases the accuracy of the diagnosis of DDR. ARA group was used as a conventional treatment option. Although statistically significant difference in pre- and post-treatment values was obtained in all the three groups, CSS group patients showed consistent clinically effective responses and more significant improvement in the subsequent follow-up visits than SS group.¹⁶

V. CONCLUSION

From the above results, the authors concluded that in comparison to the tens therapy and pharmacotherapy, occlusal splint was the most effective in managing patients with Temporomandibular Joint Pain and Dysfunction.

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